

Oxidative Behaviour of Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate towards Acid Permanganate in the Absence and Presence of Benzyl Alcohol

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The oxidative behaviour of sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) towards permanganate in the absence and presence of benzyl alcohol has been investigated in perchloric acid medium. The reaction is first order with respect to $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ and $[\text{SDS}]$ in the oxidation of SDS and the rate increases with an increase in $[\text{HClO}_4]$. For the SDS oxidation of benzyl alcohol the reaction is first order with respect to $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$ as well as [benzyl alcohol], but a complex order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ has been observed. Different thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated. In the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by this oxidant in SDS environment, the phase separation model has been employed to understand the oxidation process.

Amphiphiles have been found to catalyse a number of reactions^{1–4}. It has been observed that the hydrolysis of different esters are catalysed^{5–7} by the presence of surfactants. These have also been found to catalyse many oxidation and reduction reactions^{8–12}, as well as condensation reactions¹³. Such reactions in presence of micelles have been used on a preparative scale. Recently some investigations have been carried out on the kinetics and mechanism of some micellar catalysed reactions^{6,7,11,12}. The present report deals with the reaction of permanganate with SDS in the absence and presence of benzyl alcohol in perchloric acid medium with an idea to understand the mechanistic behaviour in micellar environment.

Results and Discussion

For the oxidation of SDS, effect of changing substrate concentration was studied at four different temperatures and at constant $[\text{MnO}_4^-]$, $[\text{HClO}_4]$ and $[\text{NaF}]$ of 1×10^{-3} , 0.1 and 2×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ respectively. The plot of pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}^s) versus $[\text{SDS}]_0$ at each temperature gives a straight line passing through the origin (Fig. 1) indicating that the reaction is first order

Fig. 1. Dependence of pseudo-first order rate constant on $[\text{SDS}]_0$ for the oxidation of SDS. Plots of k_{obs}^s against $[\text{SDS}]_0$ at different temperatures; $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-1}$ mol dm⁻³, $[\text{NaF}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³.

with respect to SDS. The plot of $(k_{\text{obs}}^s - k_{\text{obs}}^{\text{cmc}})$ versus micelle concentration $[\text{S}_n]_0$ at each temperature gives straight line passing through the origin (Fig. 2). The values of k^m (equation 1) were evaluated

Fig. 2. Dependence of pseudo-first order rate constant on the micellar concentration for the oxidation of SDS. Plots of $(k_{\text{obs}}^s - k_{\text{obs}}^{\text{cmc}})$ against $[S_n]_o$ at different temperatures; $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaF}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

from the slopes of the linear plots in Fig. 2. The values of k^w were calculated from the kinetic results below cmc. The values of k^w and k^m/N (where N is aggregation number⁷, assumed to be 84) at four different temperatures are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF SDS IN AQUEOUS AND MICELLAR PSEUDO-PHASE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temperature K	$10^2 k^w$	$10^2 k^m/N$
293	0.494	0.479
298	0.702	0.664
303	1.235	1.22
307.5	1.89	1.83

The rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol in presence of SDS was studied at varying concentrations of benzyl alcohol but at constant concentrations of other reactants, SDS and temperature. In order to compare the results, the rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol in absence of SDS was also studied under comparable conditions. The results recorded in Table

2 show that the values of pseudo-first order rate constant in presence of SDS (k_{ψ}) is higher than that in absence of SDS (k_1^R), thus indicating that the rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol is catalysed by SDS. The rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol with varying $[\text{SDS}]_o$ (from 0.005 to 0.05 mol dm^{-3}) but constant reactant concentrations was also studied at four different temperatures. The plots of pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{ψ}) values against $[\text{SDS}]_o$ are shown in Fig. 3.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION OF BENZYL ALCOHOL IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF SDS
 $[\text{SDS}]_o = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaF}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 Temp = 298 K

$[\text{PhCH}_2\text{OH}]$ (10^2 mol dm^{-3})	0.2	0.5	0.75	1.0	1.5	2.0
k_1^R (10^4 s^{-1})	1.87	4.27	6.25	9.14	12.7	16.6
k_{ψ} (10^4 s^{-1})	2.4	6.93	9.4	13.2	18.6	26.4

Fig. 3. Dependence of pseudo-first order rate constant on $[\text{SDS}]_o$ for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol. Plots of k_{ψ} against $[\text{SDS}]_o$ at different temperatures; $[\text{MnO}_4^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{PhCH}_2\text{OH}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaF}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The influence of $[H^+]$ on the rate of oxidation of surfactant was studied. The values of k_{obs}^S was found to increase with an increase in $[HClO_4]$ in the region $(0.1-1.0) \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ but at constant $[SDS]$, $[MnO_4^-]$, $[NaF]$ and temperature of 1×10^{-2} , 1×10^{-3} , $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 303 K respectively.

The influence of temperature on the rate of oxidation of SDS by MnO_4^- in perchloric acid medium was studied. The plot of $\log(k_2^S/T)$ (where $k_2^S = k_{obs}^S/[SDS]_0$) versus $1/T$ is linear in the oxidation of SDS. The values of enthalpy of activation (ΔH_2^{\ddagger}) and entropy of activation (ΔS_2^{\ddagger}) for the oxidation of SDS were evaluated to be $(68 \pm 4) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(-55 \pm 14) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The influence of temperature on the rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol in absence and presence of SDS was also studied. In absence of SDS, a plot of $\log(k_2^R/T)$ (where $k_2^R = k_1^R/[PhCH_2OH]$) against $1/T$ was employed to find out the activation enthalpy followed by entropy of activation which are $(61 \pm 4) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(-59 \pm 14) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively, in aqueous phase. In presence of SDS, the plots of $1/(k_{\psi} - k_1^R)$ versus $1/([SDS]_0 - \text{cmc})$ at four different temperatures are shown in Fig. 4. From the linear

Fig. 4. Dependence of pseudo-first order rate constant on $[SDS]_0$ for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol in the micellar pseudo-phase. Plots of $1/(k_{\psi} - k_1^R)$ against $1/([SDS]_0 - \text{cmc})$ at different temperatures; $[MnO_4^-] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[NaF] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

portion of the graph at higher SDS concentrations, the values of K and k_1^R were evaluated at four

different temperatures. The values of the association constants (K) were found to vary $(0.38-1.230) \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in the temperature range studied. The values of the second order rate constants (k_2') were determined followed by the evaluation of the activation parameters in the micellar pseudo-phase which are $(80 \pm 4) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(15.5 \pm 14) \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

Potassium permanganate may oxidise both the single units of SDS in the aqueous phase as well as the micellar aggregates. The linear plots as shown in Fig. 1, indicate that permanganate ion does not associate with the micelles to form any complex. Following Menger's model⁵ it may be suggested that the counter ions (Na^+) of the anionic micelle help MnO_4^- to enter slightly into Stern layer⁷ and the MnO_4^- oxidises the alcoholic group (produced by the hydrolysis of SDS). The rate law may be suggested by equation (1),

$$k_{obs}^S = k^w \cdot \text{cmc} + k_m [S_n]_0 \quad (1)$$

where k^w and k^m are second order rate constants for the oxidation of SDS in aqueous phase and micellar pseudo-phase respectively. The equation may be rearranged as

$$k_{obs}^S = (k^w + k^m/N) \cdot \text{cmc} + k^m/N [SDS]_0 \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) justifies the linear plots in Fig. 2 as $(k^w + k^m/N)$ values are found to be small (Table 1) so as to make the first term on right-hand-side in equation (2) negligible as compared to the second term.

In the oxidation of benzyl alcohol in presence of SDS, the phase separation model of Menger and Portnoy^{5,12} was employed to understand the oxidation process. According to Menger and Portnoy, the catalysis in presence of a micelle would occur according to the following scheme :

The substrate R, forms an association complex with micelle and k_1^R and k_1' are the pseudo-first order rate constants for the oxidation of substrate in aqueous

and micellar pseudo-phase respectively; K is known as the association constant of the substrate with micelle. If the above scheme is operative, the observed pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{ψ}) is given as

$$k_{\psi} = \frac{k_1^R + k_1'K ([\text{SDS}]_0 - \text{cmc})}{1 + K ([\text{SDS}]_0 - \text{cmc})} \quad (4)$$

or, on rearrangement,

$$\frac{1}{k_{\psi} - k_1^R} = \frac{1}{k_1' - k_1^R} + \frac{1}{(k_1' - k_1^R)K ([\text{SDS}]_0 - \text{cmc})} \quad (5)$$

The plots of $1/(k_{\psi} - k_1^R)$ versus $1/([\text{SDS}]_0 - \text{cmc})$ at four different temperatures (Fig. 4) reveal that these are not linear over the complete range of micellar concentration studied. However, it is evident that the plots are linear over the higher range of surfactant concentrations (viz. $[\text{SDS}]_0 \geq 0.02$ mol dm⁻³) with positive slopes and intercepts. It seems plausible that benzyl alcohol undergoes protonation in the acidic medium and the association of protonated benzyl alcohol with the anionic micelles will involve energetically favourable electrostatic as well as hydrophobic-hydrophobic interaction⁷. There are literature evidences^{14,15} to indicate that alkanols and aryl alcohols undergo protonation during the oxidation by chromium(VI) in perchloric acid medium. It should be noted that the enthalpy of activation for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol in the micellar pseudo-phase is higher than that in the aqueous phase contrary to the observation that the rate is faster in the micellar pseudo-phase than in the aqueous phase. This is to be expected if the oxidation reaction is entropy-controlled rather than an enthalpy-controlled one. The experimentally obtained entropy of activation values as found in the present investigation corroborate the above contention.

Experimental

Sodium dodecyl sulphate, perchloric acid, potassium permanganate, potassium iodide, sodium fluoride, sodium thiosulphate were of A.R. grade. Benzyl alcohol (Merck) was further purified by distillation just before use. All solutions were made in double distilled water.

The investigations were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions in which the substrate concentration was in large excess to that of permanganate and the acidity of the reaction mixtures was adjusted by the addition of perchloric acid. Since in permanganate oxidations, intermediate valence states of manganese can introduce complications, reactions were carried out in the presence of a large excess of F⁻, which is known to suppress¹⁶ the reactivities of Mn^{II} and Mn^{IV} by complexation. The reaction rate was monitored by withdrawing an aliquot from the reaction mixture at known intervals of time and quenching the reaction by adding it to a known excess of standard potassium iodide solution followed by back-titration of the liberated iodide with a standard sodium thiosulphate solution. The pseudo-first order rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$. The rate of oxidation of SDS alone at its cmc value was subtracted from the total rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol in presence of SDS in order to find out the rate of oxidation of benzyl alcohol in presence of surfactant. This was done because the micellar aggregates are almost completely bound to benzyl alcohol (because of high value of the association constant K) and hence not oxidised by permanganate.

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